

Prosnow API

Overview

Description of prosnow API

Tags

Authentication

Operations about authentication with JWT

Definitions

Get the definitions of configurations for snow modelling

Ski resorts

Get informations about ski resorts

Tracks

Get informations about tracks

SRUs

Get informations about SRUs

Snow depth

Get the SRU's initialisation snow depth

Water consumption

Get the SRU's initialisation water consumption

Weather forecast

Get the weather forecast for a skiresort

Predictions

Get the data for 1 SRU

Paths

GET /skiresorts Get data for all ski resorts

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Success	No Links

Code	Description	Links
401	You are not allowed to access the Prosnow service	No Links

Type	Name	Scopes
apiKey	jwt	

GET /skiresorts/{resort_id} Get data for one ski resort

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	resort_id <i>required</i>	Ski resort id	integer

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Success	No Links
401	You are not allowed to access the Prosnow service	No Links

Type	Name	Scopes
apiKey	jwt	

POST /auth/login Get a Json Web Token for User

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
query	password <i>required</i>	User password	string
query	email <i>required</i>	User mail address	string

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Get a JWT token	No Links
401	Invalid credentials	No Links

POST /auth/logout Log the user out (Invalidate the token)

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Logged out	No Links

POST /auth/refresh Refresh a token.

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Get a new JWT for the current user	No Links
401	You are not allowed to renew a token	No Links

Type	Name	Scopes
apiKey	jwt	

GET /auth/me Get the authenticated User

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Get my user informations	No Links
401	You are not allowed to access the Prosnow service	No Links

Type	Name	Scopes
apiKey	jwt	

GET /definitions/configurations Get definitions of all configurations available

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Success	No Links

Code	Description	Links
401	You are not allowed to access the Prosnow service	No Links

Type	Name	Scopes
apiKey	jwt	

GET /definitions/configurations/resort/{resort_id} Get all configurations for a ski resort

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	resort_id <i>required</i>	Ski resort id	integer

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Get the geojson with the track geometry and properties	No Links
401	You are not allowed to access the Prosnow service	No Links

Type	Name	Scopes
apiKey	jwt	

GET /forecast/resort/{resort_id} Get available weather forecast for 1 resort

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	resort_id <i>required</i>	Resort id	integer

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Success	No Links
401	You are not allowed to access the Prosnow service	No Links

Type	Name	Scopes
apiKey	jwt	

POST /forecast/resort/{resort_id} Upload one NetCDF

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	resort_id <i>required</i>	Resort id	integer

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Success	No Links
401	You are not allowed to access the Prosnow service	No Links

Type	Name	Scopes
apiKey	jwt	

GET /forecast/resort/{resort_id}/{filename} Download weather forecast cdf files

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	filename <i>required</i>	File Name with extension (only zip or gzip files)	string
path	resort_id <i>required</i>	Resort id	integer

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Success	No Links
401	You are not allowed to access the Prosnow service	No Links

Type	Name	Scopes
apiKey	jwt	

GET /snowdepth/resort/{resort_id} Get sru initialisation for 1 resort

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	resort_id <i>required</i>	Resort id	integer

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Success	No Links
401	You are not allowed to access the Prosnow service	No Links

Type	Name	Scopes
apiKey	jwt	

POST /snowdepth/resort/{resort_id} Insert Initialisation snow depth for a set of SRUs

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	resort_id <i>required</i>	Resort id	integer

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Success	No Links
401	You are not allowed to access the Prosnow service	No Links

Type	Name	Scopes
apiKey	jwt	

GET /snowguns Get informations for all allowed Snowguns

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Get the geojson with the Snowgun geometry and properties	No Links
401	You are not allowed to access the Prosnow service	No Links

Type	Name	Scopes
apiKey	jwt	

GET /snowguns/geojson Get geometries in geojson format for all allowed Snowguns

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Get the geojson with the Snowgun geometry and properties	No Links
401	You are not allowed to access the Prosnow service	No Links

Type	Name	Scopes
apiKey	jwt	

GET /snowguns/resort/{resort_id} Get snowguns informations on a ski resort

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	resort_id <i>required</i>	Ski resort id	integer

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Get the geojson with the snowgun geometry and properties	No Links

Code	Description	Links
401	You are not allowed to access the Prosnow service	No Links

Type	Name	Scopes
apiKey	jwt	

GET /snowguns/resort/{resort_id}/geojson Get snowguns geometries in geojson format on a ski resort

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	resort_id <i>required</i>	Ski resort id	integer

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Get the geojson with the snowgun geometry and properties	No Links
401	You are not allowed to access the Prosnow service	No Links

Type	Name	Scopes
apiKey	jwt	

GET /snowguns/{snowgun_id} Get informations for one snowgun

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	snowgun_id <i>required</i>	Snowgun id	integer

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Get the geojson with the snowgun geometry and properties	No Links
401	You are not allowed to access the Prosnow service	No Links

Type	Name	Scopes
apiKey	jwt	

GET /analyses/sru/{id} Get analyse data for 1 SRU, every days

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	id <i>required</i>	SRU id	integer

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Success	No Links
401	You are not allowed to access the Prosnow service	No Links

Type	Name	Scopes
apiKey	jwt	

GET /analyses/sru/{id}/day/{day} Get analyse data for 1 SRU for 1 day

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	id <i>required</i>	SRU id	integer
path	day <i>required</i>	Analyse day in date format yyyy-mm-dd	string

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Success	No Links
401	You are not allowed to access the Prosnow service	No Links

Type	Name	Scopes
apiKey	jwt	

GET */analyses/day/{day}* **Get data for all SRU, every configurations for 1 day**

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	day <i>required</i>	Analyse day in date format yyyy-mm-dd	string

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Success	No Links
401	You are not allowed to access the Prosnow service	No Links

Type	Name	Scopes
apiKey	jwt	

DELETE */analyses/resort/{id}/destroyall* **Delete all analyse data for 1 resort**

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	id <i>required</i>	Ski resort id	integer

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Success	No Links
401	You are not allowed to access the Prosnow service	No Links

Type	Name	Scopes
apiKey	jwt	

GET /analyses/snow/sru/{id} Get analyse snow data for 1 SRU, every days

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	id <i>required</i>	SRU id	integer

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Success	No Links
401	You are not allowed to access the Prosnow service	No Links

Type	Name	Scopes
apiKey	jwt	

GET /analyses/snow/sru/{id}/day/{day} Get analyse snow data for 1 SRU for 1 day

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	id <i>required</i>	SRU id	integer
path	day <i>required</i>	Analyse day in date format yyyy-mm-dd	string

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Success	No Links
401	You are not allowed to access the Prosnow service	No Links

Type	Name	Scopes
apiKey	jwt	

GET /analyses/snow/day/{day} Get analyse snow data for all SRU, every configurations for 1 day

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	day <i>required</i>	Analyse day in date format yyyy-mm-dd	string

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Success	No Links
401	You are not allowed to access the Prosnow service	No Links

Type	Name	Scopes
apiKey	jwt	

DELETE /analyses/snow/resort/{id}/destroyall Delete all analyse data for 1 resort

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	id <i>required</i>	Ski resort id	integer

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Success	No Links
401	You are not allowed to access the Prosnow service	No Links

Type	Name	Scopes
apiKey	jwt	

GET /analyses/weather/sru/{id} Get analyse weather data for 1 SRU, every days

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	id <i>required</i>	SRU id	integer

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Success	No Links
401	You are not allowed to access the Prosnow service	No Links

Type	Name	Scopes
apiKey	jwt	

GET /analyses/weather/sru/{id}/day/{day} Get analyse weather data for 1 SRU for 1 day

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	id <i>required</i>	SRU id	integer
path	day <i>required</i>	Analyse day in date format yyyy-mm-dd	string

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Success	No Links
401	You are not allowed to access the Prosnow service	No Links

Type	Name	Scopes
apiKey	jwt	

GET /analyses/weather/day/{day} Get analyse weather data for all SRU, every configurations for 1 day

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	day <i>required</i>	Analyse day in date format yyyy-mm-dd	string

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Success	No Links
401	You are not allowed to access the Prosnow service	No Links

Type	Name	Scopes
apiKey	jwt	

DELETE /analyses/weather/resort/{id}/destroyall Delete all analyse data for 1 resort

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	id <i>required</i>	Ski resort id	integer

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Success	No Links
401	You are not allowed to access the Prosnow service	No Links

Type	Name	Scopes
apiKey	jwt	

GET /climatology/sru/{id} Get clim data for 1 SRU, every days

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	id <i>required</i>	SRU id	integer

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Success	No Links
401	You are not allowed to access the Prosnow service	No Links

Type	Name	Scopes
apiKey	jwt	

GET /climatology/sru/{id}/day/{day} Get clim data for 1 SRU for 1 day

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	id <i>required</i>	SRU id	integer
path	day <i>required</i>	clim day in date format yyyy-mm-dd	string

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Success	No Links
401	You are not allowed to access the Prosnow service	No Links

Type	Name	Scopes
apiKey	jwt	

GET /climatology/day/{day} Get data for all SRU, for 1 day

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	day <i>required</i>	clim day in date format yyyy-mm-dd	string

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Success	No Links
401	You are not allowed to access the Prosnow service	No Links

Type	Name	Scopes
apiKey	jwt	

DELETE /climatology/resort/{id}/destroyall Delete all clim data for 1 resort

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	id <i>required</i>	Ski resort id	integer

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Success	No Links
401	You are not allowed to access the Prosnow service	No Links

Type	Name	Scopes
apiKey	jwt	

GET /srus Get informations for all allowed SRUs

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Get the geojson with the SRU geometry and properties	No Links
401	You are not allowed to access the Prosnow service	No Links

Type	Name	Scopes
apiKey	jwt	

GET /srus/geojson Get geometries in geojson format for all allowed SRUs

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Get the geojson with the SRU geometry and properties	No Links
401	You are not allowed to access the Prosnow service	No Links

Type	Name	Scopes
apiKey	jwt	

GET /srus/resort/{resort_id} Get SRUs informations on a ski resort

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	resort_id <i>required</i>	Ski resort id	integer

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Get the geojson with the SRU geometry and properties	No Links
401	You are not allowed to access the Prosnow service	No Links

Type	Name	Scopes
apiKey	jwt	

GET /srus/resort/{resort_id}/geojson Get SRUs geometries in geojson format on a ski resort

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	resort_id <i>required</i>	Ski resort id	integer

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Get the geojson with the SRU geometry and properties	No Links
401	You are not allowed to access the Prosnow service	No Links

Type	Name	Scopes
apiKey	jwt	

GET /srus/{sru_id} Get informations for one SRU

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	sru_id <i>required</i>	SRU id	integer

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Get the geojson with the SRU geometry and properties	No Links
401	You are not allowed to access the Prosnow service	No Links

Type	Name	Scopes
apiKey	jwt	

GET /predictions/snow/sru/{id} Get snow data for 1 SRU, every configurations, every days

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	id <i>required</i>	SRU id	integer

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Success	No Links
401	You are not allowed to access the Prosnow service	No Links

Type	Name	Scopes
apiKey	jwt	

GET /predictions/snow/sru/{id}/day/{day}/hour/{hour} Get snow data for 1 SRU, every configurations for 1 day

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	hour <i>required</i>	Forecast hour in format hh:mm:ss	string
path	id <i>required</i>	SRU id	integer
path	day <i>required</i>	Forecast day in date format yyyy-mm-dd	string

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Success	No Links
401	You are not allowed to access the Prosnow service	No Links

Type	Name	Scopes
apiKey	jwt	

GET

/predictions/snow/sru/{id}/day/{day}/hour/{hour}/configuration/{configuration} **Get snow data for 1 SRU, 1 day and 1 configuration**

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	hour <i>required</i>	Forecast hour in format hh:mm:ss	string
path	configuration <i>required</i>	Configuration number (1 to 34)	string
path	id <i>required</i>	SRU id	integer
path	day <i>required</i>	Forecast day in date format yyyy-mm-dd	string

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Success	No Links
401	You are not allowed to access the Prosnow service	No Links

Type	Name	Scopes
apiKey	jwt	

GET /predictions/snow/day/{day}/hour/{hour} **Get snow data for all SRU, every configurations for 1 day**

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	hour <i>required</i>	Forecast hour in format hh:mm:ss	string
path	day <i>required</i>	Forecast day in date format yyyy-mm-dd	string

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Success	No Links
401	You are not allowed to access the Prosnow service	No Links

Type	Name	Scopes
apiKey	jwt	

GET

/predictions/snow/day/{day}/hour/{hour}/configuration/{configuration} Get snow data for all SRU, 1 configuration for 1 day and one hour

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	hour <i>required</i>	Forecast hour in format hh:mm:ss	string
path	configuration <i>required</i>	Configuration number (1 to 34)	string
path	day <i>required</i>	Forecast day in date format yyyy-mm-dd	string

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Success	No Links
401	You are not allowed to access the Prosnow service	No Links

Type	Name	Scopes
apiKey	jwt	

DELETE /predictions/snow/resort/{id}/destroy **Delete snow data for 1 resort before current day**

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	id <i>required</i>	Ski resort id	integer

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Success	No Links
401	You are not allowed to access the Prosnow service	No Links

Type	Name	Scopes
apiKey	jwt	

DELETE /predictions/snow/resort/{id}/destroyall **Delete all snow data for 1 resort**

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	id <i>required</i>	Ski resort id	integer

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Success	No Links
401	You are not allowed to access the Prosnow service	No Links

Type	Name	Scopes
apiKey	jwt	

GET /predictions/weather/sru/{id} Get weather data for 1 SRU, every days

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	id <i>required</i>	SRU id	integer

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Success	No Links
401	You are not allowed to access the Prosnow service	No Links

Type	Name	Scopes
apiKey	jwt	

GET /predictions/weather/sru/{id}/day/{day}/hour/{hour} Get weather data for 1 SRU for 1 day

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	hour <i>required</i>	Forecast hour in format hh:mm:ss	string
path	id <i>required</i>	SRU id	integer
path	day <i>required</i>	Forecast day in date format yyyy-mm-dd	string

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Success	No Links
401	You are not allowed to access the Prosnow service	No Links

Type	Name	Scopes
apiKey	jwt	

GET /predictions/weather/day/{day}/hour/{hour} **Get weather data for all SRU for 1 day**

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	hour <i>required</i>	Forecast hour in format hh:mm:ss	string
path	day <i>required</i>	Forecast day in date format yyyy-mm-dd	string

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Success	No Links
401	You are not allowed to access the Prosnow service	No Links

Type	Name	Scopes
apiKey	jwt	

DELETE /predictions/weather/resort/{id}/destroy **Delete weather data for 1 resort before current day**

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	id <i>required</i>	Ski resort id	integer

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Success	No Links
401	You are not allowed to access the Prosnow service	No Links

Type	Name	Scopes
apiKey	jwt	

DELETE /predictions/weather/resort/{id}/destroyall Delete all weather data for 1 resort

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	id <i>required</i>	Ski resort id	integer

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Success	No Links
401	You are not allowed to access the Prosnow service	No Links

Type	Name	Scopes
apiKey	jwt	

GET /tracks Get informations for all allowed Tracks

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Get the geojson with the Track geometry and properties	No Links
401	You are not allowed to access the Prosnow service	No Links

Type	Name	Scopes
apiKey	jwt	

GET /tracks/geojson Get geometries in geojson format for all allowed Tracks

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Get the geojson with the Track geometry and properties	No Links
401	You are not allowed to access the Prosnow service	No Links

Type	Name	Scopes
apiKey	jwt	

GET /tracks/resort/{resort_id} Get tracks informations on a ski resort

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	resort_id <i>required</i>	Ski resort id	integer

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Get the geojson with the track geometry and properties	No Links
401	You are not allowed to access the Prosnow service	No Links

Type	Name	Scopes
apiKey	jwt	

GET /tracks/resort/{resort_id}/geojson Get tracks geometries in geojson format on a ski resort

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	resort_id <i>required</i>	Ski resort id	integer

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Get the geojson with the track geometry and properties	No Links

Code	Description	Links
401	You are not allowed to access the Prosnow service	No Links

Type	Name	Scopes
apiKey	jwt	

GET /tracks/{track_id} Get informations for one track

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	track_id <i>required</i>	Track id	integer

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Get the geojson with the track geometry and properties	No Links
401	You are not allowed to access the Prosnow service	No Links

Type	Name	Scopes
apiKey	jwt	

GET /definitions/variables Get definitions of all prosnow variables

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Success	No Links
401	You are not allowed to access the Prosnow service	No Links

Type	Name	Scopes
apiKey	jwt	

GET /definitions/variables/active Get definitions of all variables active in demonstrator

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Success	No Links
401	You are not allowed to access the Prosnow service	No Links

Type	Name	Scopes
apiKey	jwt	

GET /definitions/variables/mapping Get definitions of all variables mapped in demonstrator

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Success	No Links
401	You are not allowed to access the Prosnow service	No Links

Type	Name	Scopes
apiKey	jwt	

GET /definitions/variablemapclasses Get definitions of variablerenderer for the map

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Success	No Links
401	You are not allowed to access the Prosnow service	No Links

Type	Name	Scopes
apiKey	jwt	

GET /definitions/variablemapclasses/by_resort Get definitions of all variablemapclasses for a variable

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Success	No Links
401	You are not allowed to access the Prosnow service	No Links

Type	Name	Scopes
apiKey	jwt	

GET /definitions/variablethresholds Get definitions of variable thresholds for the demonstrator

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Success	No Links
401	You are not allowed to access the Prosnow service	No Links

Type	Name	Scopes
apiKey	jwt	

GET /definitions/variablethresholds/by_resort Get definitions of all variablethresholds for a variable

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Success	No Links
401	You are not allowed to access the Prosnow service	No Links

Type	Name	Scopes
apiKey	jwt	

GET /waterconsumption/resort/{resort_id} **Get sru initialisation for 1 resort**

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	resort_id <i>required</i>	Resort id	integer

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Success	No Links
401	You are not allowed to access the Prosnow service	No Links

Type	Name	Scopes
apiKey	jwt	

POST /waterconsumption/resort/{resort_id} **Insert Initialisation water consumption for a set of SRUs**

Parameters

Type	Name	Description	Schema
path	resort_id <i>required</i>	Resort id	integer

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Success	No Links
401	You are not allowed to access the Prosnow service	No Links

Type	Name	Scopes
apiKey	jwt	

Components